

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [2024-SCIENCE-BFSP, Work Package 6
- BioDiv-FAIR-Checker: Raising FAIRness of European biodiversity data
through ELIXIR-aligned standards, services, and training]

M6.2 A FAIRness evaluation of representative entries in ENA, BioSample, and DiSSCo

Tier: Science

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Executive Summary

Biodiversity data are important for understanding and conserving the natural world, yet they are often fragmented, heterogeneous, and difficult to reuse. The FAIR principles provide a framework for improving the management and sharing of biodiversity data. However, generic FAIR assessment tools may not capture the specific needs and practices of the biodiversity community. To address this gap, the BioDiv-FAIR-Checker (BioDiv-FC) project aims to enhance the FAIRness assessment of biodiversity data by developing biodiversity-aware profiles and machine-actionable recommendations. In this report, we present the results of a preliminary FAIR assessment of biodiversity data resources using the FAIR-Checker tool. We evaluated a sample of biodiversity data resources from various communities and research infrastructures, including ERGA, BOLD, LifeWatch ERIC, eLTER, and DiSSCo. The global FAIR scores obtained ranged from 16.7% to 45.8%, with most resources suffering from the lack of machine-readable metadata, which is essential for their FAIRness. This highlights the need for better metadata management and the sharing of best practices in the context of biodiversity data, as proposed by the BioDiv-FC project.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JSON-LD
Schema.org	Schema.org is a collaborative, community activity with a mission to create, maintain, and promote schemas for structured data on the Internet, on web pages, in email messages, and beyond. http://schema.org
RDF	Resource Description Framework https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
ERGA	European Reference Genome Atlas
GGBN	Global Genome Biodiversity Network
iBOL	International Barcode of Life

Supporting Documents

- Gaignard, A., Rosnet, T., de Lamotte, F., Lefort, V., & Devignes, M. (2023). FAIR-Checker: supporting digital resource findability and reuse with Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Web standards. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-023-00289-5>
- BioDiv-FC Kick-off meeting slides: <https://albangaignard.github.io/assets/pdf/2026-BioDivFC-Kickoff-2026.pdf>
- M6.1 Milestone: [ELIXIR Milestone Report - M6.1.docx](#)

Introduction

Biodiversity data are crucial for understanding and conserving the natural world, yet they are often fragmented, heterogeneous, and difficult to reuse. The FAIR principles provide a framework for improving the management and sharing of biodiversity data. However, generic FAIR assessment tools may not capture the specific needs and practices of biodiversity communities. To address this gap, the BioDiv-FAIR-Checker (BioDiv-FC) project aims to enhance the FAIRness assessment of biodiversity data by developing biodiversity-aware profiles and machine-actionable recommendations.

However, to objectively demonstrate improvements shown through the BioDiv-FC project, it is essential to make an initial, even naïve, FAIR assessment of biodiversity resources used and produced by the community. This will provide a baseline for comparison and help identify areas for improvement throughout the project. The goal of this document is to present the results of a preliminary FAIR assessment of biodiversity data resources, using the FAIR-Checker tool, and to discuss the implications for the BioDiv-FC project.

Material and methods

Automated FAIR assessment

[FAIR-checker](#) is a web-based tool that evaluates the FAIRness of web accessible digital resources. Users provide resolvable web page URLs or DOIs whose content they wish to assess for FAIRness. FAIR-Checker then consumes the embedded metadata therein to assess the FAIRness of the initially submitted URLs. It provides both a global score and fine-grained results for each of the FAIR sub-principles [1]. FAIR-Checker follows web search engines' recommendations for describing the content of web pages with semantic metadata, including but not limited to Schema.org. Technically, it consumes RDF metadata either expressed in RDFa, microdata, or JSON-LD formats. FAIR-Checker runs multiple checks to evaluate the compliance of metadata across all dimensions of

the FAIR principles, providing a clear view of metadata FAIRness. For instance, the Findability assessment is measured by multiple metrics (F1A, F1B, F2A, F2B), which evaluate the Findability of the web resource based on the presence of certain metadata and their compatibility with controlled vocabulary or domain-specific ontologies. The Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable dimensions are evaluated in similar ways, allowing Fair-Checker to provide a detailed score for each FAIR (sub)principle individually, alongside a global FAIRness score. In addition to a web interface, FAIR-Checker also provides a web API to automate the batch FAIR assessment of a list of web pages. For this preliminary assessment, we used the FAIR-Checker API in a Jupyter notebook¹ to evaluate the FAIRness of a sample of biodiversity data resources.

Benchmark dataset

During the BioDiv-FC project kick-off meeting, we discussed with all project partners the most relevant biodiversity data repositories and the kind of hosted resources. Project milestone M6.1 more precisely describes the data repositories evaluated as a result of community-specific meetings. For each community, we identified and evaluated the following resources:

1. **ERGA**, which relies on the [ENA](#) and [BioSamples](#) registries to actually store sequences as well as sample metadata. Four web resources were identified:
 - EMBL-EBI entry:
<https://portal.erga-biodiversity.eu/organism/SAMEA112797446>,
 - ENA entry:
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/SAMEA112797446>,
 - BioSamples entry:
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA112797446>,
 - BioSamples structured data entry:
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples/SAMEA112797446.ldjson>
2. **BOLD (from the iBOL consortium)**, which makes accessible individual records through barcodes as well as full datasets. Two web resources were identified:
 - BOLD entry: <http://portal.boldsystems.org/record/CHOLH011-12>,
 - BOLD dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5883/DP-Latest>,
3. **LifeWatch ERIC**,
 - Landing page of the Metadata Catalogue:
<https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadatalogue/dc512697-ed50-40c5-a3cd-1774000444b9>

¹ <https://github.com/IFB-ElixirFr/FAIR-checker/blob/master/notebooks/BiodivEval.ipynb>

- RDF machine-readable export:
<https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/srv/api/records/dc512697-ed50-40c5-a3cd-1774000444b9/formatters/rdf?output=xml>
4. **eLTER**,
 - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.82159/gt66-zt98>
 5. **DiSSCo**,
 - Landing page <https://doi.org/10.3535/ZVR-CRA-1Y1>
 - DOI metadata <https://doi.org/10.3535/ZVR-CRA-1Y1?noredirect>

Results

Figure 1: A systematic FAIR assessment over typical online biodiversity resources, as identified in the project milestone M6.1.

Figure 1 shows that the overall scores span from 16.7 % – 45.8 . Apart from a single resource that scored 45.8 %, every other entry falls at the lower end of this range. Since all evaluated resources are web accessible, they are all considered by FAIR-Checker as compliant with the F1A and A1.1 sub-principles, but the majority fail to comply with the other sub-principles, which results in a very low global score. In practice, this means that FAIR-Checker was not able to find and consume any machine-readable metadata for these resources, which is a critical issue for their FAIRness.

One example of the limitations to better scoring is exemplified by the LifeWatch RDF export

<https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/srv/api/records/dc512697-ed50-40c5-a3cd-1774000444b9/formatters/rdf?output=xml>). While this should be consumable by FAIR-Checker, the records are actually not valid RDF/XML and therefore cannot be processed. This is clearly a technical issue that can be easily fixed on the data registry side, but it also highlights the importance of providing valid machine-readable metadata for FAIRness as well as automated tools for checking the validity of metadata. As this work progresses, we intend to record these types of issues, and point to means of remediation through specific documentation, possibly linked to from the FAIR-Checker results summaries.

Only one resource (the BioSamples entry) obtained a score above 40%, meaning that very few biodiversity resources expose machine-readable metadata. For the benchmark entry hosted in the BioSamples registry, FAIR-Checker was able to find and consume metadata. All individual metrics are reported in a machine-readable format ([45.83% FAIR](#)). Most noticeably, the BioSamples entry is missing a reference to a license (A1.2, R1.1) and to provenance metadata (R1.2), which are critical for data reuse. Figure 2 reports the individual scores obtained for each sub-principle. Note that providing a license and provenance metadata (A1.1, R1.1, R1.2) would help in increasing the global FAIRness score.

Principle	Test	Result	Recommendation	Details
F1A: Unique IDs	Check	FAIR principle F1A 2/2		i
F1B: Persistent IDs	Check	FAIR principle F1B 2/2		i
F2A: Structured metadata	Check	FAIR principle F2A 1/2	You should provide discoverability oriented metadata with one of the Read more	i
F2B: Shared vocabularies for metadata	Check	FAIR principle F2B 1/2	You should express all your metadata with properties coming from Read more	i
A1.1: Open resolution protocol	Check	FAIR principle A1.1 2/2		i
A1.2: Authorisation procedure or access rights	Check	FAIR principle A1.2 0/2	You should describe the access policy in metadata by using at least one of the Read more	i
I1: Machine readable format	Check	FAIR principle I1 1/2	You should provide discoverability oriented metadata with one of the Read more	i
I2: Use shared ontologies	Check	FAIR principle I2 1/2	You should express all your metadata with properties coming from Read more	i
I3: External links	Check	FAIR principle I3 0/2	You should enrich your metadata with more diversified external links. Here we Read more	i
R1.1: Metadata includes license	Check	FAIR principle R1.1 0/2	You should include information about license in your metadata using one of Read more	i
R1.2: Metadata includes provenance	Check	FAIR principle R1.2 0/2	You should include information about provenance in your metadata using one Read more	i
R1.3: Community standards	Check	FAIR principle R1.3 1/2	You should express all your metadata with properties coming from Read more	i

Figure 2: Detailed FAIR assessment report for the BioSamples JSON-LD metadata file.

Discussion and future works

This preliminary assessment of the FAIRness of biodiversity data resources using the FAIR-Checker tool highlights several critical issues.

First, most of the evaluated resources lack machine-readable metadata, which is essential for their FAIRness. This suggests that there is a need for better metadata management and sharing practices in the biodiversity community. For data registries under active development, such as ERGA, it would be interesting to instrument the HTML rendering code with JSON-LD content following the Bioschemas recommendations. This would significantly improve the FAIRness with a minimal

development effort, benefiting from the experience of flagship Elixir resources such as TeSS, bio.tools or WorkflowHub, already exposing Bioschemas markup.

Second, even when metadata is available, it may not be complete (BioSamples registry) or compliant with standards (LifeWatch ERIC), which can hinder the reuse of the data. This underscores the importance of developing biodiversity-aware profiles and machine-actionable recommendations to improve the FAIRness of biodiversity data.

As a continuation of this work, within the BioDiv-FAIRChecker project, we plan to:

1. Update the Bioschemas BioSample profile with Biodiversity community needs in terms of mandatory, recommended, and optional properties, following the two most used ENA checklists, being ERC000011 (as a minimal set) and (ideally) ERC000053 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>). This includes better mapping these checklists to the [Schema.org](https://schema.org) / Bioschemas ontology.
2. Develop a FAIR-Checker biodiversity plugin that will
 - Provide biodiversity-specific recommendations for the generic FAIR assessment results.
 - Implement through SHACL a set of biodiversity-specific metadata completeness checks, based on the updated Bioschemas profile, and ENA checklists. The results will be displayed both as a detailed report and possibly as a metadata completeness badge for this specific biodiversity profile.
3. Improve metadata retrieval from external sources by leveraging DataCite content negotiation and the FAIR Signposting approach.
4. Report results back to UK and CH partners for the development of material on the importance of metadata and data management practices. This material will be used in future community meetings to raise awareness on the importance of FAIRness in biodiversity genomics research.

Importantly, it is crucial to involve the biodiversity community, both data producers and consumers, in the development and sharing of best practice. To that end, we aim to:

1. Develop a bioschemas 'biosample' type and engage the community to ensure that it includes all 'properties' that are essential across the biodiversity community represented in this project. This is in progress, and the 'draft' type of biosample nears release for public feedback.
2. Having agreed upon a necessary property set ('type'), we will generate a biosample 'profile', which will express which properties are mandatory, recommended or optional, as well as their cardinality (how many times they can

appear), together with values that those properties can have that are valid or expected.

3. Having agreed upon a profile, we will seek use case partners from our stakeholders to prototype implementations of the biosample profile, enabling us to measurably express the FAIR improvement levels.

For each of these stages, we anticipate a mixture of surveys, online workshops, f2f events or discussions, as well as 'show and tell' informational broadcasts to showcase our approach, and to encourage a wider adoption of this approach. Furthermore, we envision that this approach is more broadly adoptable by other communities or user groups, providing any number of nuanced FAIRness evaluation ground in existing and developing community best practices.

References

[1] Wilkinson, S. R., Alogalaa, M., Belhajjame, K., Crusoe, M. R., de Paula Kinoshita, B., Gadelha, L., ... & Goble, C. (2025). Applying the FAIR principles to computational workflows. *Scientific data*, 12(1), 328.